

APPLICATION OF ACOUSTIC EMISSION TECHNIQUES FOR THE INVESTIGATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF GRP COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Abstract - Acoustic emission (A.E.) represents a very attractive and promising technique for detecting flaws, studying material degradation and monitoring crack initiation and formation. Composite materials, moreover, appear to be ideal for the exploitation of A.E. techniques as several brittle failure modes occur before the catastrophic failure. What this paper means to produce is an investigation into the behaviour of glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) specimens with different fibre orientation by means of rising load tests, and to eventually infer some relationships between A.E. data and the stresses responsible for the various failure modes in the material being tested.

INTRODUCTION

Material study techniques based on Acoustic Emission (A.E.) detection, i. e. surface "auscultation" of the vibrational elastic energy released by propagating damages in the material, allow the facing of problems of difficult solution such as the "live" monitoring and investigation of deformation and fracture processes and the non destructive evaluation of materials including detection and localization of possibly present defects (1).

A.E. techniques are extremely promising for the solution of such problems, especially in the case of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP). These materials seem to be ideal for A.E. applications as various modes of fragile fracture of "noisy" character operate in them at the same time when the sample or the part is brought to failure (2). A.E. methods, as is generally recognized, can detect with high sensitivity signals coming from these different fracture modes as well as locate with sufficient precision the damages being sources of emission. More critical, although more desirable, is the discrimination among fracture modes and the evaluation of their relative importance in relation to the final failure.

The present paper means to investigate these potentialities of A.E. techniques which, if confirmed and translated into quantitative relations between A.E. data and fracture mode dependent material properties, would allow a better understanding of fracture mechanisms. Such understanding is indispensable both for a correct structural design and for an efficient application of A.E. techniques to the field of non destructive testing.

EQUIPMENT, SPECIMENS, AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Equipment

The experimental equipment comprises an Instron Universal Testing Machine (98.000 N), an A.E. detection system and various recording apparatuses.

Emissions were detected by a piezoelectric resonant transducer (Brüel - Kjaer 4344; fundamental frequency 70 kHz). The transducer was held on the specimen with adhesive tape and acoustically coupled with high-vacuum silicone grease. Transducer output was preamplified by 40 dB (Dunegan 1801 preamplifier) and high-pass filtered (cut-off frequency 20 kHz).

Preamplified signals were then feeded into a variable gain amplifier designed and made at the Istituto di Tecnologie, University of Naples, as well as the signal processing unit. The design and making of these two instruments are detailed in (3). The amplifier characteristics are as follows: gain 0 - 60 dB, band width 20 kHz - 2 MHz, maximum output amplitude 15 V. The signal processing unit includes a variable threshold (0,5 - 1,5 V) and a counter providing two counting modes: total or event counting. A time base allows the operation of the counter for the evaluation of A.E. count rate.

A.E. data were recorded on an X - Y pen recorder (Yokogawa Technicorder 3083). Main amplifier output was also simultaneously feeded into a RMS voltmeter (Hewlett - Packard 3400A), whose analogic output was recorded on a multiple channel galvanometric recorder (Bell - Howell Oscillograph 5 - 137), and into an oscilloscope (Hewlett - Packard 1707B) for A.E. activity visualization.

The Instron Machine was employed to tensile load the specimens at a displacement rate of $1,66 \times 10^{-3}$ m/s (0,1 cm/min) which was kept the same for all tests.

A block diagram of the instrumentation system is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 - Block diagram of the instrumentation system

Specimens

In order to study the failure mechanisms and behaviour of glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) materials with different fibre orientations, 6 types of specimens were selected. All specimens were made by superimposition of 4 unidirectional E-glass fibre layers preimpregnated with poliester resin (produced by GI.VI.DI., Brugherio, Milano, Italy) with fibres slanted by chosen angles. All laminates were designed to be symmetrical and equilibrated. The selected stacking sequences were: $(0^\circ)_4$, $(\pm 10^\circ)_s$, $(\pm 20^\circ)_s$, $(\pm 30^\circ)_s$, $(\pm 45^\circ)_s$, $(\pm 60^\circ)_s$. The laminates were first softened in hot air at 100°C and then hot-pressed for approximately 1 hour at 160°C and $0,3\text{ N/mm}^2$ pressure.

The actual test samples were cut from the laminates with a diamond disk saw and their average size was: width 23 mm, length 150 mm, thickness 0,8 mm. The fibre volume fraction was 0,65. Plexiglass tabs were bonded to the specimens in order to avoid damage between the test machine grips. The specimens length between the tabs was 75 mm. The transducer was positioned approximately midway along the specimen.

Experimental procedures

Before starting with the actual tests, simulation studies were conducted in order both to verify the A.E. instrumentation system and to investigate the material response; they consisted in the feeding into the sample of signals of known characteristics and in the examination of the various output parameters of the instrumentation. These simulation studies are better detailed in (3).

The A.E. instrumentation was set up for all tests in the following manner: gain 100 dB, threshold voltage 1 V. Four specimens of each kind of laminate were tensile tested. For each test the following graphs were simultaneously recorded versus time: stress, RMS voltage, and A.E. total count (n_t) or count rate (\dot{n}). On a certain number of specimens tests aiming at confirming the Kaiser effect validity were performed.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The major observations and data of all tests are summarized in Table I.

Table I - Summary of experimental results

type of lam.	test no.	A.E. par.	activity initiation (% of u.s.)	burst activity initiation (% of u.s.) - n_t^*	activity increase before final failure (% of u.s.) - n_t^*	ultimate stress - n_t at failure* σ (N/mm ²)
0°	32	\dot{n}	9%	54% -	95% -	1,040 -
0°	33	\dot{n}	26% (°)	48% -	95% -	950 -
0°	34	n_t	4%	39% 4,4 x 10 ³	96% 0,5 x 10 ⁶	1,040 1,4 x 10 ⁶
0°	35	n_t	2%	43% 149 x 10 ³	97% 1,1 x 10 ⁶	950 1,3 x 10 ⁶
+10°	22	n_t	21% - 70%**	75% 23 x 10 ³	98% 1,6 x 10 ⁵	483 2,3 x 10 ⁵
+10°	23	n_t	15% - 63%**	71% 5,4 x 10 ³	97% 1,3 x 10 ⁵	426 2,1 x 10 ⁵
+10°	24	\dot{n}	27% - 65%**	72% -	97% -	472 -
+10°	25	\dot{n}	14% - 70%**	75% -	97% -	484 -
+20°	12	n_t	10% - 60%**	none -	98% 2,8 x 10 ⁴	277 3,8 x 10 ⁴
+20°	13	n_t	13% - 67%**	none -	99% 2,9 x 10 ⁴	374 9,6 x 10 ⁴
+20°	14	\dot{n}	11% - 79%**	none -	98% -	366 -
+20°	15	\dot{n}	15% - 58%**	none -	99% -	310 -
+30°	37	\dot{n}	30%	79%*** -	99% -	218 -
+30°	38	\dot{n}	22%	61%*** -	98% -	266 -
+30°	39	n_t	32%	79%*** 11 x 10 ³	99% 8,8 x 10 ⁴	233 9,8 x 10 ⁴
+30°	40	n_t	29%	67%*** 20 x 10 ³	99% 10 x 10 ⁴	237 14 x 10 ⁴
+45°	18	\dot{n}	45%	none -	none -	91 -
+45°	19	\dot{n}	45%	none -	none -	82 -
+45°	20	n_t	42%	none -	none -	63 3,3 x 10 ⁵
+45°	21	n_t	40%	none -	none -	97 1,5 x 10 ⁵
+60°	42	n_t	39%	none -	none -	32 1,5 x 10 ⁴
+60°	43	n_t	51%	none -	none -	30 1,9 x 10 ⁴
+60°	44	\dot{n}	39%	none -	none -	26 -
+60°	45	\dot{n}	45%	none -	none -	27 -

* only where applicable; ** significant activity initiation; *** intermediate increase; (°) preloaded

Ultimate stress mean value, standard deviation, and parameter of scatter are summarized in Table II.

type of laminate	u. s. mean value	standard deviation	parameter of scatter (%)
0°	995 N/mm ²	5,1962	0,0522
± 10°	455 N/mm ²	3,4674	0,0762
± 20°	339 N/mm ²	5,3842	0,1588
± 30°	239 N/mm ²	2,0075	0,0842
± 45°	84 N/mm ²	1,8215	0,2179
± 60°	29 N/mm ²	0,2577	0,0896

Table II - Summary of ultimate stress mean values, standard deviations and parameters of scatter.

Experimental graphs and results are similar for all laminates of the same kind. Thus for each type of specimen only two Figures showing the A.E. parameters (total count n_t and count rate \dot{n}) plus stress and, in some cases, RMS voltage versus time have been presented.

It is useful to observe that the RMS vs. time diagrams are practically identical to the A.E. count rate vs. time diagrams, as in fact was expected. This was true for all tests; nevertheless RMS and A.E. parameters were recorded simultaneously in many cases as a verification of the good operation of the A.E. instrumentation.

In stress vs. time diagrams some load drops are visible, mainly in the case of 0° specimens; these load drops correspond to strong variations in both the RMS voltage and A.E. parameters diagrams. They may stand for damages of major importance in the material (e. g. fibre failures) but, especially in the case of load drops at low values of stress, they may also be due to specimen slipping between the test machine grips or to reinforcing tabs debonding from the specimens. This phenomenon will be investigated in the near future using tabs of different materials (aluminium) and different kinds of glue.

In the course of this section we intend to characterize, through the presentation of the experimental diagrams, an A.E. signature for each kind of laminate. By A.E. "signature" we mean a "set of identifiable characteristics of A.E. signals associated with a specific test article as observed with a particular instrumentation system under specified test conditions" (4).

0° samples (Fig. 2 and 3)

A significant A.E. activity starts within 10% of the ultimate stress (u.s.) and stays relatively constant during the whole test. This background activity is characterized by an average level of $\approx 10,000$ counts/s. High intensity bursts ($\approx 30,000$ counts/s) are superimposed to the background activity starting from 40 - 50% of u.s. The bursts appear slightly more approached to one another as the test proceeds. A very strong increase in activity is observed near the final failure (95 - 97% of u.s.). Total count at failure is larger than 10^6 .

Fig. 2 - 0° sample (test no. 32):
stress, RMS, A.E. count
rate.

Fig. 3 - 0° sample (test no. 34):
stress, RMS, A.E. total
count.

$\pm 10^\circ$ samples (Fig. 4 and 5)

A first indication of A.E. activity is observed at about 15 - 25% of u.s. A somewhat more significant activity starts at about 65 - 70% of u.s. High intensity bursts (30.000 + 40.000 counts/s) are observed at 70 - 75% of u.s. An increase in activity is finally observed near the failure point (97 - 99 of u.s.). With what concerns the A.E. signature, a background activity and a burst activity are present during the test as for the 0° specimens, but while the latter is actually similar to the one in the 0° specimens, the former increases as the test proceeds. Total count at failure amounts to $2 + 3 \times 10^5$.

Fig. 4 - $\pm 10^\circ$ sample (test no. 22):
stress, A.E. total count.

Fig. 5 - $\pm 10^\circ$ sample (test no. 24):
stress, A.E. count rate.

$\pm 20^\circ$ samples (Fig. 6 and 7)

The first signs of A.E. activity are noticed at about 10% of u.s. in the form of isolated bursts of low intensity (7,000 + 9,000 counts/s). A more significant activity starts at about 60 - 80% of u.s. An increase in the activity occurs just before the final failure (98% of u.s.). High intensity bursts are not observed during the tests. Total count at failure is $n_t \approx 10^5$.

Fig. 6 - $\pm 20^\circ$ sample (test no. 13):
stress, A.E. total count.

Fig. 7 - $\pm 20^\circ$ sample (test no. 14):
stress, A.E. count rate.

$\pm 30^\circ$ samples (Fig. 8 and 9)

A significant A.E. activity starts at 20 - 30% of u.s. The A.E. activity shows a maximum around 60 - 80% of u.s., then decreases slightly, stays constant and eventually increases very near the final failure (99% of u.s.). High intensity bursts are rather rare and the A.E. signature appears much more compact and homogeneous than for the preceding laminates. Total count at failure is $n_t \approx 10^5$. The intermediate maximum of activity occurs at $n_t \approx 10^4$.

Fig. 8 - $\pm 30^\circ$ sample (test no. 38):
stress, RMS, A.E. count rate.

Fig. 9 - $\pm 30^\circ$ sample (test no. 39):
stress, RMS, A.E. total
count

$\pm 45^\circ$ samples (Fig. 10 and 11)

A.E. activity starts at about 40 - 45% of u.s. During the test, A.E. activity increases slightly and steadily; neither sharp variations of activity nor medium or high intensity bursts are observed. An increase in activity is observed only at the failure point. Total count is greater than 10^5 .

$\pm 60^\circ$ samples (Fig. 12 and 13)

A.E. activity before the final failure is scarce notwithstanding the rather high gain of the amplification system (100 dB). The first signs of activity appear between 40 and 50% of u.s. At failure point however a certain increase in the activity is observed. Total count at failure is $n_t \approx 10^4$.

Fig. 10 - $\pm 45^\circ$ sample (test no. 18): stress, A.E. count rate.

Fig. 11 - $\pm 45^\circ$ sample (test no. 21): stress, A.E. total count.

Fig. 12 - $\pm 60^\circ$ sample
(test no. 43): stress,
A.E. total count.

Fig. 13 - $\pm 60^\circ$ sample
(test no. 45): stress,
A.E. count rate.

ANALYSIS

The A.E. parameters (total count and count rate) trends during the tests, i. e. the A.E. signatures, are positively similar for specimens of the same kind and are markedly different for specimens of different types, as can be seen from the previously shown figures.

In order to investigate the possibility of correlating these marked differences with various mechanisms responsible in turn for the failures inside the composite, Table III has been compiled. It shows, for each type of laminate under examination,

type of lam.	u. s. mean value σ (N/mm ²)	coeff. σ_1 (N/mm ²)	coeff. σ_2 (N/mm ²)	coeff. τ_{12} (N/mm ²)
0°	995	1 995	0 0	0 0
$\pm 10^\circ$	455	1,03 469	- 0,006 - 3,6	0,047 21,4
$\pm 20^\circ$	339	1,04 354	- 0,036 - 12,2	0,133 45,1
$\pm 30^\circ$	239	1,024 244	- 0,023 - 5,5	0,262 62,5
$\pm 45^\circ$	83,6	0,75 63	0,25 20,9	0,488 40,8
$\pm 60^\circ$	28,8	0,309 9	0,703 20,2	0,46 13,2

Table III - Mean values of σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} at failure.

the mean values of σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} acting respectively parallel, perpendicular and tangential to the fibres at failure. The σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} values are obtained by multiplying the ultimate stress mean value by a suitable coefficient calculated using the curves for the determination of the stresses present in each layer of symmetrical and equilibrated laminates subject to in-plane loading (5). The graph presented in Fig. 14 illustrates the variation of σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} at failure as a function of fibre inclination.

Fig. 14 - Variation of σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} at failure as a function of fibre inclination

In 0° specimens σ_1 is the obvious responsible for the final failure as σ_2 and τ_{12} are zero; with what concerns the other kinds of laminate, it is not as simple to single out a unique stress responsible for the final failure because one ought to resort to a strength criterium. It is however possible to specify the principal stresses which partake in the final failure of the specimen.

Examining Fig. 14 there results that for ± 30° laminates σ_1 is very low, σ_2 is negative (compressive) and τ_{12} is very high; one may infer that the last is the predominant stress provoking failure. For ± 60° laminates, σ_2 appears to be the prevailing stress provoking failure. For ± 10° and ± 20° specimens the prevalent stresses are σ_1 and τ_{12} ; we may assume that the latter has more relevance as to the final failure because σ_1 , although somewhat high in value, is notably inferior to the value found for 0° specimens. For ± 45° laminates, the prevalent stresses provoking failure are both σ_2 and τ_{12} with the same relevance as to the final failure.

Bearing in mind that in GFRP composites three main fracture modes operate (6): (a) fibre failure, (b) matrix failure and (c) fibre-matrix debonding, we may presume that σ_1 is responsible for the (a) mode, σ_2 for the (b) mode and τ_{12} for the (c) mode.

On the basis of these considerations Table IV summarizes the predominant fracture mechanisms operating in each kind of laminate under examination.

Type of laminate	Fracture mechanisms
0°	Fibre failure
±10°	Fibre-matrix interface and fibre failure
±20°	Fibre-matrix interface and fibre failure
±30°	Fibre-matrix interface failure
±45°	Fibre-matrix interface and matrix failure
±60°	Matrix failure

Table IV - Fracture mechanisms operating in the laminates under examination.

It is now possible to explain the marked differences in the various A.E. signatures illustrated by the experimental graphs and described above.

In 0° specimens only σ_1 is present during the test. Thus the very strong increase in A.E. activity at final failure can be associated with a general breaking of fibres. The background activity, practically constant during the test, can be associated with matrix and fibre deformation. High intensity bursts, appearing in an advanced test stage, can represent isolated breakings of misaligned fibres.

In ± 30° specimens, τ_{12} is responsible for the failure. The absence of high intensity bursts can be explained with the absence of fibre breakings. The characteristic intermediate increase in A.E. activity can be linked up with the first yielding of the fibre-matrix interface. The decrease and the subsequent almost constant trend in A.E. activity, can be associated with the rubbing between fibres and matrix following the first yielding of their interface. The final increase in activity, about as high as the intermediate increase, can be explained with the final debonding between fibres and matrix that leads to the ultimate failure.

In ± 60° specimens the prevalent stress is σ_2 . Thus the much lower A.E. activity is explicable with the minimum energy content of signals proceeding from matrix cracking. The absence of high intensity bursts implies the absence of fibre breakings.

In ± 10° specimens both τ_{12} and σ_1 are responsible for failures, although the first has more relative relevance. High intensity bursts are present in an advanced test stage and can be associated with isolated fibre failures. The moderate and somewhat irregular final increase in A.E. activity may indicate a final failure due to the ultimate fibre-matrix debonding.

In ± 20° specimens the stress state is analogous to the previous case (τ_{12} and σ_1 prevail, τ_{12} having more relevance). The possible rupture of isolated fibres during the test is accounted for by the bursts in the A.E. graphs and the final increase can still be correlated with a failure due to fibre-matrix debonding. It must be observed that the overall A.E. activity is lower than for the previous case as however was expected because a ± 20 laminate is less resistant than a ± 10° one.

Finally in $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens both τ_{12} and σ_2 are significantly present and responsible for failure. The absence of high intensity bursts can be explained with the absence of fibre breakings. The scanty overall A.E. activity is most likely due to the predominance of σ_2 dependent matrix failure mechanisms as well as the absence of a decided A.E. activity increase at final failure. On the other hand τ_{12} can be considered responsible for the observed, though low, background activity, also characterized by low intensity bursts, which could correspond to fibre-matrix debonding and rubbing mechanisms.

KAISER EFFECT

By Kaiser effect we mean the irreversibility of A.E., i. e. "the absence of detectable A.E. until previously applied stress levels are exceeded" (4). The validity of the Kaiser effect for composite materials is controversial: some authors state the effect to hold true, some disclaim it and some obtained mixed results. For a more detailed illustration of the question see (7).

In order to verify the Kaiser effect in GFRP composites, tests to the purpose were carried out on one specimen for each kind of laminate. Specimens were loaded and kept at constant stress level until no more A.E. signals were detected; then they were unloaded and reloaded and the stress level at which A.E. started again was recorded. Results were summarized in Table VI and it can be noted that A.E. activity starts again at the same stress level previously attained or at a lower one with a tolerance of [+0% - 30%].

Type of laminate	Preload (% of u.s.)	A.E. resumption (% of u.s.)	A.E. resumption with same derivative (% of u.s.)
0°	26%	26%	28%
$\pm 10^\circ$	20%	14%	-
$\pm 20^\circ$	66%	50%	74%
$\pm 30^\circ$	46%	46%	-
$\pm 45^\circ$	40%	40%	-
$\pm 60^\circ$	44%	36%	-

Table VI - Kaiser effect validity tests.

On 0° and 20° specimens the stress level at which A.E. shows the same derivative with respect to time that had been previously attained was recorded and reported in the last column of Table VI. This condition was attained at a stress level higher by $\approx 10\%$ than the previously applied one. The data are obviously too few to have a definite meaning; further investigation on the subject is certainly needed.

CONCLUSION

Symmetrical and equilibrated GRFP specimens with fibre orientation variable between 0° and 60° were examined. The following parameters were recorded versus time: stress, RMS voltage, A.E. total count and count rate. On the basis of the experimental results, characterizing A.E. signatures for the different kinds of laminates were specified. Such signatures were then correlated with fracture mode

responsible stresses in the material under examination. Kaiser effect validity was finally investigated.

This research is part of a larger program aiming at the standardization of A.E. tests and data under static and dynamic conditions in order to provide quantitative information useful for structural design and non destructive testing applications. The next step in the program is concerned with A.E. detection during fatigue testing of GFRP composites.

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